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PRESERVING AUTHENTIC TRADITIONAL FOOD FOR HOSPITALITY PRODUCTS' QUALITY IMPROVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

In the complex structure of the hospitality industry, food continues to occupy a central place. Satisfaction with the food is a significant prerequisite for overall satisfaction with the hospitality product. In the conditions of modern globalization trends in all spheres of human life, traditional food and culinary traditions become significant tools for differentiation from similar products on the market and gaining a competitive edge.

The aim of this paper is to identify possible ways to preserve and promote authentic culinary traditions, leading to improved quality and competitiveness in hospitality products. In doing so, current efforts to preserve authentic food and culinary traditions in the Republic of Macedonia will be presented through an analytical method, with specific applications in the hospitality offer. This presentation should provide insight into the level of care for this aspect of our cultural heritage, promoting diversity and maintaining a connection with the past.

KEY WORDS: traditional food, hospitality, quality, culinary tradition, authenticity

INTRODUCTION

The contemporary diet model has evolved considerably, shaped by numerous complex factors that have given rise to what is now known as "globalized food." This model crosses borders and cultural divides, quickly spreading worldwide and permeating nearly every environment. The internationalization of food, an inevitable process historically accompanying material and cultural exchanges among peoples, has transformed dietary habits by blending diverse culinary traditions into a homogenized global palate. However, alongside this widespread globalization, there are concurrent efforts to preserve the authenticity of food, particularly traditional gastronomic products.

The authenticity of traditional gastronomic products, integral to the hospitality experience, is closely linked to the authenticity of Traditional Food Products (TFPs) produced by local agriculture and other food producers within the community. These TFPs, influenced by the same factors that shape traditional cuisine authenticity, are vital in maintaining the cultural and historical integrity of regional diets.

In the Republic of Macedonia, preserving this authenticity faces several challenges, particularly within the legal-regulatory framework. Traditional cooking methods, which rely on techniques passed down through generations, risk being overshadowed by modern, technology-driven methods that prioritize efficiency over tradition. The legal system, with its costly and time-consuming procedures for registering Geographical Indications (GIs), discourages local producers from protecting their products, threatening the preservation of these traditional methods.

Gastronomic education is a critical factor in this context. Educating local producers about the significance and potential benefits of GIs, as well as their obligations, is essential for preserving the authenticity of TFPs. This education should not only focus on the technical aspects of food production but also emphasize the importance of traditional cooking methods in maintaining cultural heritage. Government initiatives should support this educational effort by facilitating the GI registration process and promoting Macedonian TFPs on an international scale.

Moreover, the lack of a coordinated approach to promoting these products, especially internationally, further diminishes Macedonia's visibility in the global market for Traditional Food. The country's rich culinary heritage, which could be a valuable asset in the hospitality and tourism sectors, remains

largely underrepresented. This calls for a unified strategy involving all stakeholders, from local producers to government bodies, to create a comprehensive approach that preserves the authenticity of Traditional Food while embracing the positive aspects of modern culinary innovations.

Analyzing these factors within the context of the Republic of Macedonia reveals that preserving traditional food authenticity requires a delicate balance between embracing globalization and maintaining cultural heritage. Integrating traditional and modern cooking methods, supported by strong gastronomic education and a coordinated promotional strategy, is key to ensuring that Macedonia's culinary traditions continue to thrive in a rapidly globalizing world.

FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE SAFEGUARDING OF TF AUTHENTICITY

Wilczyńska (2017) defines traditional products as those made using traditional recipes and unique raw materials. If something is authentic, it is real and true (Cambridge dictionary), or it is what it claims to be, genuine (American dictionary). Authentic (Greek *authentikos*) means legal, valid, truthful, certain, enforceable, and untainted (Vujaklija, 1980, p.89). Perhaps the phrase unadulterated or pure is most suited to convey TH authenticity: not blended or diluted with any additional ingredients.

“The cultural globalization in cuisine triggered the so-called process of ‘authentication’ undertaken by chefs and cooks who aim at re-establishing culinary traditions”. (Almansouri et al.2022).

Although according to one research consumers mostly accept TFP (TF products) innovations, such as: packaging, nutritional and convenience oriented innovations, the authors conclude that in some cases these innovations may damage the traditional character of the food (Guerrero et al.). Traditional food has long provided specific nourishment tailored to the needs of different groups, such as calorie-rich diets for laborers, nutrient-dense meals for children, and high-protein foods for athletes. However, as modern life has become less physically demanding, the functional need for these traditional diets has decreased. Despite this, traditional foods remain culturally significant, deeply connected to the geography, climate, and history of a region, and continue to be vital to local identity and community cohesion (Gutiérrez et al. 2022).

Traditional and modern cooking methods take very different approaches to food preparation. Traditional methods frequently rely on skills passed down through generations, such as slow-cooking, boiling, fermenting, and open-fire grilling. These approaches prioritize time and natural processes, allowing tastes to fully develop and frequently utilizing simple, locally obtained ingredients. Modern cooking methods, on the other hand, make use of advanced technology and science, such as sous vide, microwave cooking, and molecular gastronomy. These approaches promote efficiency, precision, and invention, enabling novel textures, flavors, and presentations that were not conceivable with previous procedures. While traditional cooking honors cultural history and promotes sustainability, modern approaches frequently push the bounds of culinary inventiveness and convenience.

Factors that influence the safeguarding of TF authenticity are direct, indirect and interdisciplinary:

Knowledge and education

In the definition of TF, knowledge passed down from generation to generation plays an important role. People's primary knowledge about their own TF is passed down by oral tradition and hands-on learning, and it is improved through everyday encounters in their environment. These are skills passed down from generation to generation in agriculture, farming, fishing, and other forms of natural resource extraction or cultivation. Also, understanding of how raw ingredients are transformed into finished food items, such as milling, baking, fermenting, curing, and preparing dishes. Professional knowledge for the hospitality business, specifically food and beverage outlets, is gained through formal education as well as specialized courses and trainings.²¹

In RN Macedonia, culinary is taught in secondary vocational schools within the framework of the hospitality and tourism profession. The first specialized catering school was founded in 1949 in Skopje. Today in Macedonia there are 10 secondary vocational schools in which the catering and tourism profession is studied. (Center for Vocational Education and Training, 2024).

Within the framework of higher education, Gastronomy is integrated into the study programs of four state universities and one private one. (Ministry of Education and Science, 2024) There is only one institution that realistically

²¹ One of the first culinary schools is Le Cordon Bleu founded in Paris in 1895, today considered as the largest network of culinary and hospitality schools in the world.

offers the study program of gastronomy in Macedonia²². The oldest Gastronomy study program and the only was first introduced at the Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality in Ohrid, back in 1970 (FTU - Ohrid). In the Gastronomy bachelor study, traditional food is incorporated especially in the courses: Culinary, National cuisine, and Culture and food. (FTU Ohrid). At the Master studies in Gastronomy and food technology (Joint studies with the Faculty of Biotechnical Sciences in Bitola), cooking techniques and technologies are studied, among other things, as well as other courses in the field of gastronomy and food technology, which also include TF. (FTU - Ohrid)

Recording and systematizing the TF knowledge

This way of TF authenticity preserving began with the recording of oral traditions from generation to generation in the form of recipes. For example: recipes for cheeses or dairy products crafting, for bread and pastries, sausages, condiments, or pickled items or cooked dishes. This is how the original recipes, ingredients, techniques for processing or cooking methodologies were documented.²³ This preservation of authentic TF knowledge has evolved over the centuries from hand-written recipes and instructions to digital platforms or databases to store and share documented information, websites, blogs, apps or other digital tools to reach wider audience and ensure easy accessibility. Today, in the conditions of a developed TFPs market, all traditional cultivation procedures and processes of raw TF and their processing in TFPs are subject of research in cultural heritage, ethnology, sociology, history, food science, food chemistry, ethnobotany, ethnopharmacology, legal and regulatory aspects etc. These has resulted in a vast literature, scientific and professional papers and publications of TF systematized knowledge, contributing to the TF authenticity, available print and online. (UKIM, UKLO, UGD repositories).

²² According to the report of Alain Henriët (a French retired higher education general inspector) and Isabelle Frochot (university professor in the field of tourism and hospitality) who investigated the tourism and hospitality higher education study programs in the country as part of the EU twinning project “Further support to the implementation of the National Qualifications Framework” MK IPA 17 SO 01 21, the only higher educational institution that offers gastronomy study program is the Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality Ohrid.

²³ One of the earliest cookbooks in recorded history dates back to the 1st century CE. The work is conventionally known as Apicius, and officially titled: *De re coquinaria* (The art of cooking). The book comprises more than 400 recipes, and it is estimated that it has been preserved in numerous editions ever since.

Legal regulation for TF protection

The 2003 Convention for safeguarding of the intangible cultural heritage, also refer the TF and culinary practices as an integral components of culture heritage. (Text of the Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage 2003). “Perhaps the latest frontier of food regulation is food as heritage which implies its description and framing as a cultural phenomenon rather than merely as a biological one”. (Lixinski, 2018 p.469). The 2003 CSICH gives a framework for safeguarding and encourages UNESCO member states to develop strategies, programs and legislation according to the Convention, to protect their TF authenticity.

The EU's interest in TF, due to the developed TFPs market, has resulted in numerous legal regulations that other countries are trying to adopt in order to protect their TFPs and harmonize their legislation with the European one. The concept of Geographical Indications (GIs) guarantees the quality of TFPs and registered products with these marks stand out from other products similar to them, which are unprotected and unregistered. (Kakurinov,p.8) “Consumers would be willing to pay more for TFPs with the certified quality label, than for a product without one. Therefore, the small scale producers and processors of this type of food should consider this attribute as a strategic tool for differentiation”. (Padilla C., et all., 2007,p.306)

Among three geographical indications (TSGs, PGI and PDO), in the current practice of the EU member states, the most unsuccessful in terms of the number of registrations is the indication for TSGs, and it is even proposed to abandon it, although it is stated that this indication can contribute for an important part of European gastronomy to be recognized and saved as gastronomy heritage (Zapallaglio, 2022).

In Macedonia, steps have been taken regarding the adjustment of the TFPs legal regulation for the protection, to the European one, primarily within the framework of the Law on the quality of agricultural products. Chapter III contains rules about quality designation and requirements and procedures for registration for PDO, PGI and TGS. (Official Gazette of RM 140/2010). This is supported by appropriate legal acts – regulations that refer to registration procedures, application forms, etc. (Official Gazette RM 134/2007; Official Gazette RM 144/2019)

“Macedonian practice seems to be still in its initial phases, although more than two decades have passed since the enactment of the 1993 IP law”. (Buchkovski, Naumovski 2017). Only two geographical indications have been registered at the national level: Ohrid cherry and Prespa apple. (Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management 2024). At the international level, the Republic of Macedonia has only four registrations under the Lisbon system: Macedonian ayvar, Krivopalanecki med, Disan Wine, and Kochanski rice (WIPO Lisbon system 2004). In terms of wines, progress is expected with the adoption of the new Law on Wine, in which, among other things, the system for the protection of geographical indications of wine is fully in line with European legislation and it is expected that they will be protected by PDO and PGI at national and international level. (RNM Government 2023).

Nongovernmental organizations

There are several international governmental organizations that plays significant roles in the protection of the TF authenticity, like: Slow food; International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM – Organic International; Cultural Survival; Ark of Taste (Slow food Foundation); Center for food safety (CFS); International Network of Eco Regions (IN.N.E.R.); Slow Food Foundation for Biodiversity.

In the Republic of Macedonia, Slow Food Makedonia shows especially fruitful results (beginnings date back to 2008). Slow food Makedonia has implemented numerous activities and projects related to food, TF, sustainable agriculture, culinary techniques, education, promotion, preservation of biodiversity, motivating the community and creating awareness for the preservation of TF as a cultural heritage. A significant result of the Organization is the Initial List of Traditional Products (Project: Creation of the Initial List of Traditional Products SILOS). The list contains 153 mapped TPs and represent a significant contribution to the process of TPs protection with "quality marks", because the material collected in the field is systematized according to European rules and regulations for product specification in order to obtain a protected mark. (Initial lists of TFPs.2019) Also, Slow food activists cataloged 36 Macedonian products in the Ark of taste (Ark of taste products in N Macedonia). At the national level, there are numerous nongovernmental organizations that are directly or indirectly engaged in the field of TF and contribute to preserving its authenticity.(Nongovernmental organizations, register).

Traditional food authenticity safeguarding events

Recognizing the importance of TF authenticity, stakeholders²⁴ often organize events through which knowledge is exchanged and awareness of the importance of TF authenticity is raised. Most often these are food festivals with different contents, which can be dedicated directly to TF, or TF can be an additional content in the event.

Food Festivals are public events aimed at celebrating specific food products. “They come with straightforward names that identify the event, the products that are promoted, the year of the festival, and the place where are it is celebrated”.(Fontefrancesco, Zocchi 2020) Like: Oktoberfest-Munich, Germany; Pizzafest-Naples, Italy; Pushkar camel Fair-Pushkar; Poutine Festival (various locations), Canada, and many other around the world.

In RN Macedonia, there are numerous events, mostly in the form of festivals related to TF, combined with an appropriate setting and additional contents, both in urban and rural areas. In total, there are 50 such events in all regions of the country. The most famous are: Epiphany - Vodici and Fishermen's Day – Ohrid; Wine and Cheese Festival – Ohrid; Ohrid Sofra – Gjomleziada, Ohrid; Kosteniada - Makedonski Brod; Praskober – Rosoman; Tikveshki vintage – Kavadarci; Pivofest – Prilep; Kochanski Rice Days-Kochani and many others (Chochoroski,2021).

Traditional food and beverage outlets

TF and beverage outlets, with their adequate menus and wine cards are TF authenticity guardians in a particular regional community. They can be different depending on their concept such as: traditional restaurants, street food vendors that specialize in TF, mobile kitchens, farm-to-table restaurants, fine dining establishments etc. Some very famous with menus based on TF are: Osteria Franceskana-Modena, Italy (Michelin guide 2024); Noma Copenhagen, Denmark (The world 50 best restaurants 2021); Sukiyabashi Jivo – Tokyo, Japan (Michelin guide 2024) and many others.

In Macedonia, there are numerous restaurants and other food and beverage outlets that primarily base their menus on the TF concept, but also those in which TF is incorporated as an option in the menus that are not only

²⁴ Local communities, cultural organizations, government agencies, non-governmental organizations, international organizations (UNESCO, FAO), educational institutions, chefs and culinary associations, tourism boards, food and agricultural organizations, local business and restaurants

traditional. According to the name, the catering facilities closest to TF restaurants would be the National restaurants - inns, which receive a special prescribed mark during registration. (Act on catering activity 2002). These restaurants have to fulfill certain conditions: to use products and materials of domestic origin, in a domestic traditional way, according to a recipe of a national, i.e. regional character; wines and other drinks must be 80% domestic; the interior arrangement, the ambience, the staff and the music should be in the spirit of the Macedonian tradition. 10 such restaurants were registered 3 years ago, which have not renewed their registration. Currently, there is no such name registered (Ministry of economy 2024).

Authentic TF – farm to table is offered within the catering services of rural households that are registered to prepare and serve hot and cold dishes, drinks and beverages mainly from their own production and tasting of wine and brandy (Act on catering activity 2002).

The examples of restaurants that preserve the authenticity of Macedonian traditional cuisine are: Kukja na mijacite (near St. Jovan Bigorski); (kukjanamijacite.mk) Kutmichevica, (village Vevchani); Dedo Dimo, (near Ohrid); Baba Cana,(Kumanovo) (babacana.mk) and many others.

Authenticity as a function of quality

TF authenticity is its main attribute and without it, TF cannot be "traditional". The described factors that affect the authenticity of TF are in close correlation with functional quality and technical quality of hospitality products. (Kotler et al. 1996). Stakeholders integrated approach toward these factors in terms of their planning, directing and controlling, can directly contribute to hospitality products quality improvement. This improves the quality of the physical TFPs, but also improves the process of delivering the service or product. It is a product made from locally produced ingredients according to methods handed down from generation to generation, prepared according to a preserved original recipe and served according to preserved customs, in dishes and ambience that correspond to the preserved tradition. The more authenticity is built into each element of these farm-to-plate processes, the greater the functional and technical quality of the traditional gastronomic product is, integrated into the hospitality product. Authentic traditional food creates a genuine experience, as well as trust and credibility which impacts overall perceived quality.

The following analysis in Macedonia examines whether the previously identified factors influencing TF authenticity, contribute to the integrated quality of hospitality products (see SWOT analysis).

<p>Strengths:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A well-developed educational system, which is based on tradition (from secondary schools to master's studies); - Well systematized and documented TF knowledge in the relevant scientific disciplines, in printed and online form; - Already well documented and recorded TF data; - Developed network of international and national nongovernmental organizations; - Existence of numerous and significant TF manifestations mainly on national level; - Existence of numerous ethnic restaurants. 	<p>Opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction of new educational programs and courses to preserve TF authenticity in the existing educational system; - Further TF promotion; - Engagement for new GIs registrations; - Further community animation and involvement for TF preservation; - Partnerships between nongovernmental relevant organizations and governmental agencies; - Greater international promotion of the existing TF manifestations, and transformation of the more significant ones into international ones; - Promotion of cultural heritage; - Creation of national portals about TF.
<p>Weaknesses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GIs registrations are associated with long and expensive procedures; - Cancellation of re-registration of registered national restaurants - inns; - Absence of visible data for the traditional restaurants registrations (according to the name); - Absence of visible data on registered rural farms that 	<p>Threats:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On-line information (blogs, some websites, social media channels, etc.) is not always correct and original in terms of recipes, ingredients, TF procedures; - Slow harmonization of the legal regulation with the European one, as well as application in practice; - Very small number of GIs registrations and only at the national level;

provide catering services of accommodation and food; - Absence of national Internet portals about TF.	- A small number of registrations according to the Lisbon system; - The dispute regarding the name of the country, with the southern neighbor (Use of the adjective Macedonian - product, wine, etc.).
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CONCLUSION

The analysis of the determined factors in the Republic of Macedonia reveals that the main challenges lie within the legal-regulatory framework, particularly in relation to the protection and promotion of Traditional Food (TF) through Geographical Indications (GIs). The current legal system is marred by expensive and time-consuming registration procedures for GIs, which serve as a significant deterrent for local producers who might otherwise be inclined to protect and market their products under this designation. This situation is further exacerbated by the lack of awareness among producers regarding the potential benefits and the legal obligations associated with GIs. As a result, there is an urgent need for targeted educational programs to inform and empower producers about the value of GIs, alongside robust government support throughout the registration process.

Moreover, the absence of a strategic, coordinated effort to promote these geographically indicated products, particularly on the international stage, significantly hampers Macedonia's visibility in the global market for Traditional Food. This lack of promotion not only diminishes the recognition of Macedonian TF abroad but also weakens its position as a valuable component of the country's hospitality and tourism sectors. Therefore, it becomes evident that a coordinated approach involving all stakeholders at the national level is crucial. Such collaboration would foster the creation of comprehensive strategies aimed at preserving the authenticity of Traditional Food, while also considering the intertwined cultural, economic, and environmental dimensions. Only through such a holistic approach can Macedonia effectively safeguard and promote its culinary heritage on both a national and international scale.

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